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CHAPTER**

ASSESSMENT OF AVAILABILITY, UTILIZATION OF ICT AS ALTERNATIVE FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF RESEARCH METHODOLOGY CURRICULUM IN UNIVERSITY OF CALABAR AMID COVID-19 PANDEMIC: PSYCHOSOCIAL IMPLICATIONS FOR TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Abstract

The present study focused on assessing availability and utilization of ICT as alternative for implementation of research methodology curriculum in the faculties of education, university of Calabar amid COVID-19 pandemic as well as the psychosocial implications for teaching and learning. Survey research design was adopted for this study; the study was conducted in University of Calabar. Population of the study consisted of the officers and lecturers in the 3 faculties of education. The study sample consisted of 85 respondents (82 lecturers and 3 faculties officers) selected through accidental sampling procedure in which the researchers visited the respondents' offices and administered the data collection instrument to those they met in their offices during the time of visit to their offices. The instrument for data collection was a check list titled "ICT Availability and Utilization Check List (ICTAUCL). The check list was face validated for suitable items being sought for. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer research questions. Findings of the present study reveal poor level of availability and utilization of ICT facilities, for implementation of research methodology curriculum in the three faculties of education in university of Calabar, with 12 points challenges perceived to be responsible for the poor situation. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations became necessary: Deans of the three faculties of education in university of Calabar, should consider taking urgent steps in collaboration with the university management to improve level of ICT facilities available in the faculties. Individual lecturers may acquire and utilize some of the critical ICT facilities for themselves, as it could make their teaching innovative and more effective. When these ICT facilities are made available, lecturers should in collaboration with the university management, enlist in training at the university ICT centre to improve their skills in utilization of ICT in teaching. University management should take steps to surmount all challenges perceived to be hindering progress in ICT utilization for teaching, in order to put the university at par with other universities in the world.

Introduction

The primary concern of any educational system is to achieve set goals for the betterment of the individuals and the society at large. To this end, the expectation of the society is for teachers to utilize resources and implement the curriculum so that students can learn and

achieve optimally. However, the changing realities of modern society have placed serious challenges on curriculum implementation. This is because the society as a vital source of the curriculum is so dynamic to the extent that emergence of new challenges is inevitable; most recently, one of such challenges is the COVID-19 pandemic which brought the entire world to its knees with many lives lost. The current COVID-19 global health crisis is unprecedented and could be considered as one of the turning points in history with tendency of shuffling social, economic, educational and psychological norms and triggering a new human era. The magnitude and speed of collapse in different activities that have followed, are unlike anything experienced in our lifetime (Gopinath 2020). For example, the crisis has caused hundreds of thousands of fatalities, tested the limits of health systems, and has put the world in a great lockdown where the global economy is experiencing the worst recession since the Great Depression 85 years ago (Gopinath 2020). With social, economic, and health systems on the verge of collapsing, it is impossible to know what the new world will look like, but its shape will depend on the decisions education stakeholders make now (Orji & Bichene, 2021).

Indefinite shut down of schools became one of the strategies adopted by several countries including Nigeria, to prevent spread of the virus. The shutdown of schools and almost all other sectors of national life, coupled with the severity of the pandemic no doubts may have had some attendant psychosocial implications on individuals and families alike. For instance, before the schools were shut down, some learners in different tertiary institutions in the state were already preparing for examinations, while some were already in the midst of examinations in which way some teachers and learners would have been stretched in one way or the other, but hanged-on to end of the semester/academic session, only to be shocked with the announcement of school shut down, meaning that they would have to return to whatever tasks were giving them challenges. The fear and panic that greeted such announcement is capable of bringing about psychosocial problems among teachers and learners. For Orji, Gbande and Ajah (2021), some of these psychological challenges that may be suffered include; anxieties, stress, depression, aggression, conduct disorder, social phobia, delinquency, especially while away from school. This is alluded to by McInerney and Mcklindens (2014) in Orji, Gbande and Ajah, (2021) who maintained that post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) can have a direct, immediate and potentially overwhelming impact on the ability of learners. Also, evidence exists that self-efficacy of the learner is altered as a result of PTSD condition. For example, a study by Ness and Vroman (2014) cited in Orji, Gbande and Ajah, (2021) revealed the effects of self-reported trauma (TB) or post trauma stress disorder (PTSD) on self-regulated learning and academic achievement for university-enrolled military service members.

When schools finally reopened, it was obvious that social distancing must be maintained among members of the school community, while teaching and learning responsibilities still needed to be discharged adequately amid the COVID-19 pandemic. As these realities emerge, the educational system must be ready to make adequate provisions for curriculum implementation, because the curriculum must surely be implemented or reviewed as need arises. Curriculum implementation is so important that

if it fails, the society fails. The process of preparing a people for the life they have to live in future essentially involves education; whether formal or informal. This makes education a universal phenomenon- formal education could hardly be achieved without a functional school system. The success of formal education in any society is hinged on the success of the school system of that society, and one important part of the school system is tertiary institutions with the school curriculum as its main agent (Ebuta and Bichene, 2019). The relationship between education and curriculum can be likened to that of Siemens twin, the two are inseparable. Curriculum is an education concept described in various ways by educationists; it is termed to have its roots in Latin. However, many definitions fall within the expectations of schools as a socio-academic institution. And this is in respect to; the purpose of the school, what is to be taught, how it is taught and to whom it is taught, as well as the effectiveness of what is taught (relevance of the entire program to the needs of individual learners and the society). A curriculum is considered the “heart” of any learning which means that schools cannot exist without a curriculum. Thus, the role of teachers in curriculum implementation is very important, yet in Nigeria the teacher seems to be relegated to the background, faced with issues ranging from poor training to poor working condition, absence of necessary facilities. This has been part of the reasons for the failures of the past, and it has to change in the current precarious situation occasioned by COVID pandemic.

Why the focus on implementation of research methodology curriculum? We think it is important to first put into proper context, what research is all about. Idika (2015); Anagbogu (2017); Idika, Offong and Uchegbue (2010); Salau (2018); Idika and Ojini (2019) all agree that research is the scientific method of identifying problems and recommendation and application of solutions to the problems. Educational research on the other hand is the systematic and scholarly application of the scientific method to the solution of educational problems. Educational research is aimed at enquiry towards the advancement of knowledge in education and learning processes. From the foregoing, it is clear that research involves activities aimed at problem solving.

Research methodology is a course thought in the third year by lecturers who are experts in the field, and offered by all learners in faculties of education at various levels irrespective of discipline of study. It is aimed at equipping learners across faculties with requisite background knowledge and skills of carrying out research and reporting of findings as they are mandated to carry out a research project in partial fulfillment of the requirements to be awarded degrees in various disciplines of study. Already, Idika, Joshua and Umoinyang (2017) noted that the skills required for efficient research writing among researchers are fast draining off the universities, and positioning the teaching of research methodology as a central issue in our curriculum could be a step in the right direction. In fact the importance of research demands adequate and effective implementation of its curriculum because if poorly implemented, learners would continue to lack basic skills of research even though they are carrying various education degrees. And the implication is that such learners would not be able to contribute meaningfully to solving problems of the

society, especially in this COVID era where a myriad of solutions are required to survive the pandemic.

Anecdotal feedbacks suggest that our current teaching and learning environment prompted by the COVID-19 virus is not that appealing in the eyes of many (Zhao, 2020). Therefore, the use of alternative teaching approaches that allow teaching and learning to go on smoothly without the teachers and learners necessarily being physically present in one location (classroom) has become imperative. In the current technology age when scientific information increases daily and technological innovation advances rapidly, it is obvious that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities will play a key role for the future of the societies. To this end, a switch over to utilization of ICT facilities as an alternative approach to curriculum implementation amid COVID has become ultimate and imperative desideratum.

Lecturers need to utilize these ICT facilities like: Power Points, projectors, computers, video machines, CD-ROMs, internet, slides, digital multimedia etc, to make teaching and learning possible and effective in the COVID era where social distancing has become highly necessary (Youdeowei, 2016), especially with the emergence of the current delta variant of COVID which medical experts have said is more virulent. Hence, to continue to depend on the usual approach to teaching and learning where lecturers and students over crowd themselves in the physical classroom is to resign to suicide mission. No doubt, introduction of ICT in curriculum implementation will come at a cost. ICT facilities need to be made available to all departments in order for lecturers to have access to optimally utilize them for curriculum implementation, a paradigm shift that could make teaching and learning more practical and interesting to learners (Alverman, 2018).

Truly, ICT has created a lot of impact on the quality and quantity of teaching and learning through its dynamic, interactive and engaging contents and it can provide real opportunities for individualized instruction (Igbokwe, Ndidiamaka, Adeline and Ngozi, 2020). According to Amuche (2015) ICT have been used for educational purposes in many countries of the world, but have not been common features in the Nigerian classrooms. As far back as 2012, Idika, Idaka and Ukpokor carried out a survey on availability and utilization of IT systems for effective teaching of sciences in secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria, and found both to be significantly low. The study strongly recommended among others the need for teachers' retraining, workshops and conference participation and increased government involvement in provision of ICT facilities. Due to the changes in world economy, emphasis has shifted from training for lifelong profession to training of computers and information technology (Idika et al, 2012; Oluwatumbi, 2015). Issues like good course organization, effective time management, self-study, collaborative learning, task oriented activities, and effective communication between actors of teaching-learning process and research activities will be enhanced by the use of ICT (Apagu & Wakili, 2015). Ndifon and Igwebuikwe (2019) found that effective teaching and learning can be carried out with or without physical contact as is hitherto the case in the traditional approach. ICT utilization in tertiary institutions will facilitate knowledge acquisition and dissemination by students within and between various disciplines. Idika et al (2012) and Fuller (2015)

agree that availability of ICT facilities is crucial for change to take place. The change here is method of teaching; according to them, facilities include anything required for implementation of the innovation, including hardware, software, supplies, funding, technical support and teaching materials. Computer aided instruction (CAI) according to Apagu and Wakili (2015) is a self-learning technique, usually offline/online, involving integration of the students with programmed instructional technique where a computer is used to present the instructional material and monitor the learning that takes place. Opportunities provided by the CAI in the classroom are in the area of drill and practice, tutorials, simulations, demonstrations, designing, data collection and retrieval, analysis of games which are essential competences for research. Oyeniran and Oyeniran (2020) aver that effective adoption and integration of ICT into teaching in schools depend mainly on the availability and accessibility of ICT facilities such as hardware, software, etc.

Therefore, this study was designed to assess the availability and utilization of ICT as alternative for implementation of research methodology curriculum in University of Calabar amid COVID-19 pandemic.

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent are ICT facilities available for implementation of research methodology curriculum in University of Calabar amid COVID-19 pandemic?
2. To what extent are ICT facilities utilized for implementation of research methodology curriculum in University of Calabar amid COVID-19 pandemic?
3. What are the challenges of ICT facilities utilization for implementation of research methodology curriculum in University of Calabar amid COVID-19 pandemic?

Method

Survey research design was adopted for this study; the study was conducted in University of Calabar. The University of Calabar is a University situated in Calabar, Cross River State-South-South Nigeria. It is one of Nigeria's second generation Federal Universities. The population of the study consists of the 3 officers and the lecturers in the 3 faculties of education. The study sample consisted of 85 respondents (82 lecturers and 3 officers) selected through accidental sampling procedure in which the researchers visited the respondents' offices and administer the data collection instrument to those they met in their offices during the time of visit. The instrument for data collection was a check list titled "ICT Availability and Utilization Check List (ICTAUCL). The check list was face validated for suitable items being sought for. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer research questions.

Results**Table 1: Availability of ICT facilities for implementation of research methodology curriculum**

ITEMS	Faculty/ Department	Personal	REMARKS
ICT Room	3	0	NA
Slide projectors	1	0	NA
Virtual library	0	0	NA
Virtual classroom app	0	0	NA
Arts studio	0	0	NA
Laptop computers	6	44	A
Statistical Apps	0	23	MA
Modems	0	14	SA
Internet (WAN)	0	0	NA
Intranet (LAN)	0	0	NA
Scanner	1	4	SA
Digital camera	0	0	NA
Film strip	0	0	NA
Internet enabled phone	0	77	A
Interactive white board	0	0	NA
Whats'APP group	5	66	A
Twitter	0	33	MA
Telegram	4	31	MA
You Tube	0	46	MA
Instagram	0	20	SA
Optical fibres	0	0	NA
Electronic notice board	0	0	NA

KEY: NA = NOT AVAILABLE, SA = SCARCELY AVAILABLE, A = AVAILABLE, MA= MODERATELY AVAILABLE

Results of data collected on availability of ICT facilities for implementation of research methodology curriculum as presented in Table I shows that the faculties have only one ICT room and the departments have none, and no lecturer has a personal ICT room. Similarly, only 1 slide projector was seen to be available at the faculties, 2 departments but none personal from the lecturers. For virtual library; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0. Virtual classroom app; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0. Also, for availability Arts studio, faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0, Laptop computers; faculties = 6, department = 0, personal = 44, on availability of statistical applications for; Modems; ; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 14, Internet (WAN); faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0, Intranet (LAN); faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0, Fax Machine; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0, Scanner; faculties = 1, department = 0, personal

= 4, Digital camera; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0, Film strip; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0, Internet enabled phone; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 77, Interactive white board; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0, WhatsApp group; faculties = 1, department = 4, personal = 66, Twitter; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 33, Telegram; faculties = 1, department = 3, personal = 0 33, You Tube; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0, Instagram; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 20, Optical fibres; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0, Electronic notice board; faculties = 0, department = 0, personal = 0.

Table 2: Utilization of ICT facilities for implementation of research methodology curriculum

ITEMS	UTILIZATION		REMARKS
	Yes	No	
ICT Room	9 (10.58)	76 (89.41)	Poor
Slide projectors	14 (16.47)	71 (83.52)	Poor
Virtual library	0 (0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
Virtual classroom app	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
Arts studio	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
Laptop computers	23 (27.05)	62 (72.94)	Fairly good
Statistical Apps	7(8.23)	78(91.76)	Poor
Modems	12(14.11)	73(85.88)	Poor
Internet (WAN)	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
Intranet (LAN)	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
Scanner	4(4.70)	81(95.29)	Poor
Digital camera	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
External storage disc	6(7.05)	79(92.94)	Poor
Film strip	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
Internet enabled phone	38(44.70)	47(87.05)	Good
Interactive white board	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
WhatsApp group	23(27.05)	62(72.94)	Fairly good
Twitter	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
Telegram	13(15.29)	72(84.70)	Fairly good
You Tube	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
Instagram	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
Optical fibres	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor
Electronic notice board	0(0.00)	85(100.00)	Very poor

Results of data for utilization of ICT facilities for implementation of research methodology curriculum as presented in Table 2 show that for ICT Room; only 9

respondents out of the 85 representing 10.58% said Yes implying that they utilize the ICT room for teaching, while 76 respondents, representing 89.41% said No implying that they do not utilize the ICT room for teaching; for utilization of Slide projectors; Yes=14 (16.47), No =71 (83.52), on utilization of virtual library; Yes = 0 (0.00), No = 85(100.00), virtual classroom app; Yes =0(0.00). No =85(100.00), Arts studio; Yes =0(0.00), No = 85(100.00), Laptop computers; Yes = 23 (27.05), No = 62 (72.94), Statistical Apps; Yes = 7(8.23), No = 78(91.76), Modems; Yes = 12(14.11), No = 73(85.88), Internet (WAN); Yes = 0(0.00), No =85(100.00), Intranet (LAN); Yes = 0(0.00), No = 85(100.00), Fax Machine; Yes = 0(0.00), No = 85(100.00), Scanner Yes =4(4.70), No = 85(100.00), Digital camera; Yes = 0(0.00), No = 85(100.00), External storage disc; Yes = 6(7.05), No =79(92.94), Film strip; Yes = 0(0.00), No =85(100.00), Internet enabled phone; Yes = 38(44.70), No = 47(87.05), Interactive white board; Yes = 0(0.00), No = 85(100.00), WhatsApp group; Yes =23(27.05), No = 62(72.94), Twitter; Yes =0(0.00), No =85(100.00), Telegram; Yes =13(15.29), No = 72(84.70), You Tube; Yes = 0(0.00), No = 85(100.00), Instagram; Yes = 0(0.00), No = 85(100.00), Optical fibres; Yes =0(0.00), No = 85(100.00), and for utilization of electronic notice board; Yes =0(0.00), No = 85(100.00).

Table 3: Descriptive analysis of challenges of ICT facilities utilization in implementation of research methodology curriculum

S/ N	Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Inadequate supply of computer hardware	85	2.71	1.06	Accepted
2	Inadequate supply of computer software.	85	3.16	0.82	"
3	Irregular power supply.	85	3.29	0.70	"
4	Lack of training in the use of ICT facilities.	85	2.70	0.63	"
5	Lack of institutional partnership with professional and cooperate bodies for technical support.	85	2.52	0.50	"
6	Poor service by internet providers.	85	2.68	0.72	"
7	Insufficient knowledge of how to use ICT.	85	2.69	0.91	"
8	Poor maintenance of available ICT facilities.	85	2.85	0.85	"
9	Bureaucratic/administrative bottleneck in funding.	85	3.06	0.75	"
10	Lack of adequate orientation on how to integrate ICT into curriculum implementation.	85	2.94	0.74	"
11	Using ICT facilities for instruction is too expensive.	85	1.92	0.82	Rejected
12	Lack of technical support to keep ICT facilities working during instruction.	85	2.84	0.83	Accepted
13	Difficulty in managing all that ICT facilities integration in the curriculum requires.	85	2.68	0.95	"
	Valid N (listwise)	85			

Cut- off Mean for decision = 2.50

Results of data collected for perceived challenges of ICT facilities utilization for implementation of research methodology curriculum as presented in Table 3 show that out of the 13 items listed, 12 items (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,12,13) were perceived by respondents as challenges impeding the utilization of ICT facilities for implementation of research methodology curriculum, while one item (item 11) was perceived not to be a challenge. Decision was taken using a cut-off Mean value > 2.50 (accept) and Mean value < 2.50 (reject).

Discussion

From the results of this study, it is obvious that the journey to availability and utilization of ICT for curriculum implementation in university of Calabar faculties of education is still far, as evident in the unavailability of such facilities which could also have been responsible for very poor level of utilization, because one cannot utilize what is not available. This position supports that of Idika et al (2012) and Oyeniran and Oyeniran (2020) who found that effective adoption and integration of ICT into teaching in schools depend mainly on the availability and accessibility of ICT facilities such as hardware, software, etc.

The consequence here is that if the COVID – 19 pandemic persists (which is most likely) given the predictions of medical and public health experts, we may witness another lock down and school shut down. If that happens, use of online teaching largely enhanced by ICT may become more compelling, in which case students from the faculties of education in university of Calabar may be deprived of the opportunity to learn with their peers in other faculties and institutions. In such a situation, learners may develop some psychosocial disorders such as phobia for failure, anxiety, trauma, low self-esteem, to mention a few, and of these could affect learners negatively. Again, even with the present situation with COVID-19, there is nothing wrong in adopting ICT in teaching and minimizing physical contact in our already overcrowded classroom. Ndifon and Igwebuikwe (2019) found that effective teaching and learning can be carried out with or without face to face contact as has been the case in the traditional approach. ICT utilization in tertiary institutions will facilitate knowledge acquisition and dissemination by students within and between various disciplines. A number of studies that had successfully supported the need for e-learning especially in the face of socio-economic uncertainties include those of Idika, Opong, Asor & Kebbi (2012); Amuche (2015); Igboke, Ndidiamaka, Adeline, Anyanwu, and Eli-Chukwu (2020). They all agree that availability of ICT facilities is crucial for change to take place and this is in the area of method of teaching, facilities (hardware, software, supplies, funding, technical support and teaching materials) required for implementation of the innovation.

Although results of findings revealed 12 out of 13 challenges examined, as perceived potential hindrances to availability and utilization of ICT, this is not insurmountable. There is no doubt that introduction of ICT in curriculum implementation will come at a cost (Igboke et al, 2020). ICT facilities need to be made available to all departments in order for lecturers to have access to optimally utilize them for curriculum implementation.

Conclusion

Findings of the present study reveal poor level availability and utilization of ICT facilities, for implementation of research methodology curriculum in the three faculties of education in university of Calabar, with 12 points challenges perceived to be responsible for the poor situation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations became necessary:

1. Deans of the three faculties of education in university of Calabar, should consider taking urgent steps in collaboration with the university management to improve level of ICT facilities available in the faculties. Individual lecturers may acquire and utilize some of the critical ICT facilities for themselves, as it could make their teaching innovative and more effective.
2. When these ICT facilities are made available, lecturers should in collaboration with the university management, enlist in training at the university ICT centre to improve their skills in utilizing ICT in teaching.
3. University management should take steps to surmount all challenges perceived to be hindering progress in ICT utilization for teaching, in order to put the university at par with other universities in the world. Some of these steps include:
 - i. ICT Infrastructures have to be put in place
 - ii. Training of staff on ICT, counseling of staff to have positive attitude toward utilization of technology tools in teaching and information sharing
 - iii. Necessary policy frameworks to support utilization have to be put in place – including provision of free WiFi connectivity or connection; subsidizing Internet subscription for lecturers, etc.
 - iv. Getting approval from the regulatory bodies like the NUC, needs also to be in place.

References

- Alverman D: (2018). *Teacher Students Mediation of Content Area Text*. Theory into Practice, 27, 142 – 147
- Amuche, A. A. (2015). Availability and utilisation of ICT resources in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ando-Kola and Jalingo, Taraba State. *Journal of Poverty, Investment and Development*, 8(1), 94-100.
- Anagbogu, G. E. (2017). *Research process in education and social sciences*. Calabar: University of Calabar Press
- Apagu, V. V. Wakili, B. A. (2015). Availability and utilization of ICT facilities for teaching and learning of vocational and technical education in Yobe State Technical Colleges. *American Journal of Engineering Research*, 4(2), 113-118.
- Bichene, C. E. and Orji, E. I. (2021). Awareness, perception and adherence to COVID-19 preventive measures among rural dwellers in Cross River State-Nigeria. *in press*.

- Ebuta, C. N. and Bichene, C. E (2019). Research based curriculum and functional education a panacea for national development. *Journal of education, university of Uyo*; 11 (1); 145 – 154
- Fuller, B: (2015). *Raising School Quality in Developing Countries: What Investments Boost Learning*.
- Gopinath, G. (2020). “The Great Lockdown: Worst Economic Downturn since the Great Depression.” IMFBlog, April14.
- Idika, D.O. (2015). Adequacy of research as quality assurance measure in Nigerian Universities. In D. I. Denga, (Ed.). *Credible Educational Response to current challenges plaguing Nigeria (pp. 319-344)*. Calabar: Rapid Educational Publishers.
- Idika, D. O., Offong, M. E., & Uchegbue, H. O. (2010). Reconstructing Educational Research in Tertiary Institutions: Strategy for sustainable Development in the third world. *The International Researcher*, 1(5), 194-205
- Idika, D., Idaka, I., & Ukpokor, C. (2012). Assessment of availability and utilization of information technology (IT) for effective teaching of science in secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. *Journal of Teacher Perspective*, 6(1), 63-74.
- Idika, D. O., Oyong, S. B., Asor, L. J., & Kebbi, J. A. (2012). E-Learning in Global Education: Challenges and Prospects *International Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 4(1), 226-230
- Idika, D. O., Joshua, M. T. & Umoinyang, I. E. (2017). Assessment of research skills among academic staff in public universities in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 16(2), 119 – 135
- Idika, D. O & Ojini, R. A. (2019). Ethical compliance in research practice among post graduate students in University of Calabar. *Assessment Journal of Education* 4 (1), 213-228.
- Igbokwe, I. C., Ndidiamaka J. Okeke-James, Adeline N. Anyanwu and Ngozi C. Eli-Chukwu (2020). Managing the Challenges to the Effective Utilisation of E-Learning as a response in COVID-19 Nigeria. *International Studies in Educational Administration (ISEA)* Vol. 48 (2) 28-34. Accessed from website: www.cceam.org. 26/04/2021
- Ndifon, R. A. and Igwebuike, O. (2019). Institutional academic culture and effective implementation of educational technology curriculum in tertiary institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development* Vol.7, No.11, pp.12-21
- Oluwatumbi, O. S. (2015). ICT literacy among vocational and technical education teachers in Kogi State Technical and Vocational Colleges: Skill gaps. *British Journal of Education*, 3(5), 21-30.

- Orji, E.I., Gbande, A. P. & Ajah, M. O. (2021). Psychological health of the learner and school achievement: Way forward. In C. E. Okwarakalu, N. E. Ajuzie, P. C. Ifegbu & C. N. Ihekweba. (Eds.). *Negating issues in educational system in Nigeria: The Way forward*. Owerri. Pp. 154-171.
- Oyeniran, S. and Oyeniran, F.M. (2020) A Descriptive Analysis of Educational Services in Nigeria during COVID-19 lockdown. *International Studies in Educational Administration* (ISEA) Vol. 48 (2) 21-27. Accessed from website: www.cceam.org. 26/04/2021
- Salau, M. O. (2018) Research and evaluation dynamics for functional education with reference to assessment and certification, science and technology, and evidence-based policy development. *Lead paper presented at the 20th Annual conference of the Association of Educational Researchers and Evaluators of Nigeria (ASSEREN) 9th – 13th July, in Abuja-Nigeria.*
- Youdeowei, T. (2016). Lack of technology adaptation, bane of education in Nigeria – Stakeholders. *Vanguard News*, Dec. 29, 2016
- Zhao, Y. (2020). “COVID-19 as a Catalyst for Educational Change.” *Prospects*